

Dyes Derived from Phenanthraquinone : Fluoreno-phenanthrazines.

BY PARESH CHANDRA DUTTA, DAMODAR PRASAD AND SATISH CHANDRA DE.

In continuation of the work of Watson and Dutt on phenanthra-phenazines (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1211) and Sircar and Dutt on phenanthranaphthazines (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1944), the present investigation was undertaken with a view to study if the complexity of the ring has any deepening effect on the colour of the monoazine dyes. The present communication deals with azine dyes obtained by condensing phenanthraquinone and its derivatives with 1:2-diaminofluorene (Diels, Schill and Tolson, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3284). The compounds prepared are all deeper in shade than those of the corresponding phenanthraphenazines and the phenanthranaphthazines. For the sake of convenience a comparison of the colours of dyeings of wool of some of these classes of compounds is given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Name of the compound.	Colour of the dyeing wool.
4-Nitrophenanthranaphthazine ...	Light yellow
Fluoreno-4-nitrophenanthrazine ...	Deep brown
4:5-Dinitrophenanthranaphthazine ...	Yellow
Fluoreno-4:5-dinitrophenanthrazine ...	Chocolate
2-Aminophenanthraphenazine ...	Yellow
Fluoreno-2-aminophenanthrazine ...	Chocolate brown
2-Hydroxyphenanthranaphthazine ...	Yellow
Fluoreno-2-hydroxyphenanthrazine ...	Chocolate

The compounds dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep blue colour and the original dyes are reprecipitated by the addition of water and in this condition they are well suited for dyeing on wool from an acid bath. They are characterised by their high melting points and their sparing solubility in alcohol and acetic acid.

The structure of these compounds can be represented by the following general formula.

For the sake of abbreviation the preparation of only one of these compounds is described and the rest, except the 2-amino- and the 4-amino-compounds where in place of acetic acid absolute alcohol was taken, being prepared in similar manners, their properties recorded in Table II.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Fluorenophenanthrazine.—Molecular quantities of phenanthraquinone and 1:2-diaminofluorene in acetic acid solutions were mixed together and boiled for 1 hour when the substance separated out as a greenish-brown crystalline precipitate which was filtered, washed with acetic acid and alcohol and recrystallised from nitrobenzene in thin brown needles, m. p. 279-80°. It is insoluble in alcohol, sparingly soluble in acetic acid and moderately soluble in pyridine. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a blue colour and dyes wool in yellow shade.

DYES DERIVED FROM PHENANTHRAQUINONE

TABLE II.
Dyes Derived from Phenanthraquinone.

Name.	Prepared from 1,2-diaminofluorene and	p	Appearance.	Crystallised from	Shade on wool.	Analysis.	
						Found.	Calc.
F-P *			Thin brown needles.	Nitrobenzene	Yellow	N, 7.40	7.60 p.c.
F-2-nitro-P		2-Nitro-p	Chocolate needles.	Pyridine	Chocolate brown	N, 10.04	10.16
F-4-nitro-P		4-Nitro-p	Greenish-brown crystalline mass.	"	Deep "	N, 10.08	10.16
F-2:7-dinitro-P		2:7-Dinitro-p	Yellow prismatic needles.	Nitrobenzene	Yellow	N, 12.13	12.22
F-4:5-dinitro-P		4:5-Dinitro-p	Chocolate brown small needles.	Pyridine	Chocolate	N, 12.15	12.32
F-2-bromo-P		2-Bromo-p	Brown crystalline mass.	Acetic acid	Brown	N, 6.10	6.26
F-2-amino-P		2-Amino-p	Brown microscopic needles.	Pyridine	Chocolate brown	N, 11.01	10.96
F-4-amino-P		4-Amino-p	"	"	Deep "	N, 10.83	10.96
F-2:7-diamino-P		2:7-Diamino-p	"	"	Yellowish "	N, 14.00	14.07
F-2-hydroxy-P		2-Hydroxy-p	Chocolate brown needles.	Acetic acid	Chocolate	N, 7.91	7.29
F-4-hydroxy-P		4-Hydroxy-p	Brown crystalline mass.	"	Greenish brown	N, 7.18	7.29
F-2:7-dihydroxy-P		2:7-Dihydroxy-p	Chocolate brown crystalline mass.	"	"	N, 6.81	7.00

* Fluorenephenanthraquinone melts at 279-80°. The rest melts above 290°.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
G. B. COLLIER,
MUNICIPALITY, (B. & O.).

Received March 29, 1932.

